

STARTING AND MANAGING A COMMUNITY RADIO STATION

**Licenses, rules, costs and sources of
revenue from the experience of our
stations in Ireland, Romania and
Portugal**

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 780890.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to gather in one place some basic knowledge about the institutional and economic framework for Community Radio in Ireland, Romania, and Portugal. In particular, we will try to summarize the main rules and regulations defining the process to obtain the licenses for broadcasting in these countries and the economic management of stations and sources of income, as well as the main initial costs experienced by the stations of the Grassroots Wavelengths project.

One of the objectives of the project is to support the communities involved in the definition of station governance strategies. From the beginning, we realised how different institutional and economic frameworks in different contexts have a strong influence in the processes of creation and management of the stations. Therefore, we considered important to describe these frameworks as simply as possible so that both the actors involved and new communities interested in starting their experience with a community radio could benefit from them.

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IRELAND

HOW TO OBTAIN A LICENSE

In Ireland a legal entity (e.g. registered company or co-operative society) can submit a request for a temporary license (a Temporary Sound Broadcasting Contract for a Temporary Sound Broadcasting Service) in every moment of the year. The request must be sent by email at least three months in advance from the potential beginning of transmissions. This license give the possibility to broadcast for not more than 30 days in a period of 12 months.

The applicants need to fill a form prepared by the Broadcasting Authority of Ireland (“the BAI”), and there is a [“guide to submission”](#) that support, step by step, in the compilation of the document. The information requested are mainly related to:

- a description of the applicant details, its ownership and control, who will manage the station.
- The description of the station:
 - programme policy statement (for instance, the philosophy of the station, how many hours of broadcasting per day, the percentage and features of speech, music (also in relation to Irish tradition and language), news, sports, etc. programs, and the contribution to the diversification of programs in the area.)
 - studios and transmission (the address of the studio (mandatory only if they, in the future, want to apply for a 100 days license), the studio equipment and the security mechanism against unauthorised access to the on-air studio, the location of the transmitter, its features, and the characteristics of the area where the antenna will be set.)
- A financial and business plan where the applicant describe the main sources of income, the projected income and the main sources of expenditure.

The document presented by our partners in Bere Island counts about 15 pages in total.

Some documents must be attached to this application:

- an indicative programme schedule with a description of how it is linked with the programme policy statement;
- a map of the studio with its features;
- the quote for libel insurance;

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- some documentations about the situation of the applicant.

EXTERNAL SUPPORT

Some sections of the application require some technical skills, for instance to define the map of the area covered by the radio signal. Support can be found in:

- BAI section on temporary licenses for feedback;
- CRAOL - The Community Radio Forum of Ireland, for support and training;
- other community radio stations.

EXPENSES, FUNDING RULES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR COMMUNITY RADIO

The applicant need to pay a levy of 750€ per calendar year. In the [guide](#) it is specified that the stations can apply for a 500€ support scheme that can be used for training, development and/or evaluation activities.

Rules

	Temporary license (30 dd)	Pilot license (100 dd)	Full license
Advertising	no ([1] footnote 5)	no ([2] footnote 7)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. no more than 50% of income is secured from commercial activity; 2. a maximum of 6 minutes advertising/ sponsorship per hour will apply; 3. stations may only broadcast advertisements which relate to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. work opportunities which exist in the specified area b. events which are to occur in the specified area c. businesses which are carried on in the specified area

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			d. services which are delivered in the specified area. ([3] p. 8)
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Temporary stations (those on 30 day or 100 day+ licences) can collect money through fundraising and sponsorship. These 2 sources need to be balanced (50% fundraising; 50% sponsorship).

Funding sources

- For the station:
 - [Temporary Radio Support Scheme](#) - for training, development and/or evaluation activities (max 500€)
 - [POBAL](#) - funding for community development (not for temporary stations)
 - [Community Employment \(CE\) Scheme](#) - It only funds staff
- For radio programmes
 - [Sound and vision](#) - Funding scheme for programmes on Irish culture, heritage etc.

Estimate of expenses incurred by Bere Island Community Radio during one year of activity¹

<i>What</i>	<i>How much</i>
Copyright music and royalties - PPI	€521.95
Rent (studio space)	€1200 (this is paid to Bere Island Heritage Group)
CRAOL membership	~€3000
BAI levy/licencing fee (€750 plus VAT (if the contractor not exceed 250k €))	€750 + VAT
Public liability insurance	€1027.50

¹ Taking advantage of the experience collected by the community, now the costs to set a new station can be lower than those here described.

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Hardware, devices...	~€700
Tot.	~€7199.45

POTENTIAL SOURCES OF REVENUE (suggested by the community in Bere Island)

- Sponsorship (maybe someone could sponsor the program “postcards from the past”).
- Sponsorship from the marine (programs on these topics).
- Radio Bingo, raffles and quiz.
- Collaboration with other stations (making programs for bigger stations?)

GENERAL RULES ABOUT COMMUNITY RADIO IN IRELAND

- Only a legal entity can apply for a 30 day license (e.g. registered company or co-operative society; no an individual or group of individuals). [4]
- To apply for a 100 day license, the legal entity should be established on a not-for-profit basis. [5]
- A broadcasting levy has to be paid. [4]
- Stations must have in place a means to make time-stamped recordings of all broadcasts and a way to store these for a minimum of 90 day.
- Can only FM broadcast on the exact dates and during the exact times specified in the licence agreement.
- Programme schedule required – percentage of time taken to each type of broadcasting as defined in the programming policy statement (PPS)
- The Applicant’s approach to developing its ability to meet the statutory requirements for news and current affairs content; specifically, 20% news and current affairs content over the total broadcast day, and, should the service broadcast for more than 12 hours per day, 2 hours between 7am and 7pm. Note that temporary community radio stations are not obliged to meet this

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requirement – but to obtain a full licence, they must show they have potential to do so.

- The applicant must have an appropriate insurance policy, as noted p.7 in the BAI licencing guide document for temporary stations. [4]
- Must have a studio (though in practice, this is really only looked at for the 100 day up licences) – p.8 in the BAI licencing guide document for temporary stations. [4,5]
- To play copyrighted music, all radio (including community radio) need to pay royalties.

[1] [Application Form Regular Temporary Service](#)

[2] [Application Form Pilot Community Temporary Service](#)

[3] [BCI Policy on Community Radio Broadcasting](#)

[4] [BAI Guide Regular Temporary Service](#)

[5] [BAI Guide Pilot Community Temporary Service](#)

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ROMANIA

HOW TO OBTAIN A LICENSE

In Romania, the audio-visual law (504/2002) define three different ranges of audio-visual license: national, regional and local. It is stated that the last serve a unique local community. However, the procedure to obtain the license is the same in the three cases. The license is granted through a contest announced publicly by CNA, the national regulator. The applicant's activity object has to be "audio-visual service".

In the case the Romanian stations involved in the project, there was also an additional initial step to accomplish: The request to integrate the frequencies related to the two villages where station had to be set in the contest list. For this reason, they introduced the project to CNA who in turn asked the counsel to ANCOM, the national organisation that manage the audiovisual spectrum. ANCOM added the two frequencies on the contest list.

In the CNA website there is a very brief and theoretical article explaining how to obtain the license. It is stated that the license is granted for a period of 9 years and can be extended of other 9 years. In order to prepare the documentation, the applicant should consult a regulator's Decision (277/2013) and the related Annexes, together with its amendments and supplements contained in other 2 decisions (614/2013 and 405/2015).

There is a template that the applicant can follow to communicate information about the station:

- information about the applicant ("legal persons of public or private law, foundations and associations without patrimony purpose, as well as authorized natural persons in keeping with law provisions");
- the name of the station;
- the broadcasting time;
- the topic of the station;
- the percentage of the different program productions and of the typology of the programs.

Other documents and material need to be attached:

- an audio file with the station identification signal;
- a very precise schedule containing the programs for everyday of the week;

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- an editorial project, with a detailed description of the philosophy of the project and of the stations together with a detailed description of every program contained in the schedule;
- an editorial strategy with the definition of the contents, role etc.;
- a financial project with the source of income, the initial investment, the advertising resources etc.;
- a technical project with the description of the technology and the equipment used;
- a document with the other licenses owned by the applicant.

In the case of our Romanian stations, the document is composed by around 40 pages.

At the contest, the applicants can be represented by a team composed by no more than 5 people, called to offer to the commission more information about the status of the applicant, the editorial strategy of the station, the resources, the equipment, the financial plan. After the presentation, the member of the CNA (a council of 11 people) vote about the possibility to give or not the license to the applicant. After the approval of CNA there will be two technical tests with ANCOM, and then the CNA provides the right to broadcast.

EXPENSES, FUNDING RULES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR COMMUNITY RADIO

Rules

1) The proportion of television advertising spots and teleshopping spots within a given clock hour shall not exceed 20%, 12 minutes respectively; in case of public television, their duration shall not exceed 8 minutes from the given time of any hour ([1] art. 35).

Estimate of expenses incurred for the setting of 1 Romanian Community Radio and one year of activity²

<i>What</i>	<i>How much</i>
Copyright music and royalties	<i>based on a calculation that considers the amount of music broadcasted but</i>

² Taking advantage of the experience collected by the communities, now the costs to set a new station can be lower than those here described.

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	<i>also costs and revenues of the station (see the Methodology in ORDA's Decision no 6/2018)</i>
Marketing (social media campaign, banners, stickers, radio sets (as gadgets distributed to the community members to cover the lack of radio devices and to promote the station))	~5000€
levy/licencing fee	~150€
Hardware, software, devices...	~4500€

POTENTIAL SOURCES OF REVENUE (suggested by the communities in Varvoru De Jos and Sfântu Gheorghe)

VdJ

- Adv and sponsorship from admin.
- Adv from private: for instance announcements about working/renting lands.
- contribution in cash and in kind from the people of the community.

SG

- Adv and sponsorship from private: for instance a sponsorship with the local touristic resort; advertise from local small business.
- Income from special projects: for instance collaboration with [Anonimul](#) film festival next year.
- contribution in cash and in kind from the people of the community.

GENERAL RULES

- Radio-broadcasters shall be legal persons of public or private law, foundations and associations without patrimony purpose, as well as authorized natural persons in keeping with law provisions ([1] art. 43).
- Radio-broadcasters of private law that are legal persons are set up and operate as companies ([1] art. 43).
- Advertising spots, including self-promoting or teleshopping ones may be included only between programs. Some exceptions are possible ([1] art. 27).
- Sponsored programs ([1] art. 34):

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- content and their scheduling shall by no means be influenced by the sponsor so as to affect the liability and editorial independence of the media services provider;
- the mention of a sponsorship agreement made known by the name or brand and/or sponsors' products/services shall be distinctly shown at the beginning, during the respective programs and at the end of the program;
- they shall not encourage directly the purchase or rental of the sponsor's or a third party's products or services, especially by special promotional references to such products or services.
- Different license:
 - National: right to broadcast the same program in a geographical area covering a potential audience of over 60% (for radio) of the country's censused population;
 - Regional: right to broadcast the same program on the territory of one or more counties without reaching the coverage stipulated in the national license;
 - Local: same program in a unique local community ([1] art. 44).
- The license is granted for a 9-year period, and may be extended every 9-years upon request under the conditions established by the Council ([1] art. 54).
- The analogue or digital audio-visual license may be ceded to a third party only with the approval of the Council and if the new holder assumes all the liabilities deriving from the license and presents the tax certificate of the company that holds the license ([1] art. 56).
- The broadcasting license may be ceded towards a third party together with the analogical audiovisual license, upon prior approval from the Council and from The National Authority for Management and Regulation in Communications, as well as upon new license holder's approval to comply with all the obligations in the license also by making proof of the revenue certificate of the company that holds the license ([1] art. 66).

[1] Law no. 504/July 11th, 2002 - The Audiovisual Law (Text in force as of November 22nd, 2009) <http://www.cna.ro/The-Audio-visual-Law,1655.html>

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PORTUGAL³

FUNDING RULES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR COMMUNITY RADIO

Rules

- Dissemination of advertising materials shall not occupy more than 20% of the total licensed program services broadcasting time per day. ([1] art. 40)
- The sponsored programming spaces must necessarily include at the beginning the express mention of this fact. ([1] art. 40)

Funding sources

- In order to ensure the possibility of expression and confrontation of the various currents of opinion, the State organizes a system of incentives for local radio activity, regulated with specific laws. These usually require previous radio broadcasting activity to have taken place for a specific amount of time.

Expenses

What	How Much
ANACOM Short term event license (40 days)	50€
ANACOM Short term event license (90 days)	116,25€

GENERAL RULES

- The following shall be deemed as purposes of the radio broadcasting activity, according to the nature, subject-matter and coverage area of the radio programme services provided:
 - A. To contribute towards public information, education and entertainment;

³ Due to the presence of particular experimental licenses and of some issues related to the management of the project, in Portugal the development of project' stations has been minimal. For this reason, also the information collected about the institutional and economical framework are not so complete as in the other two countries.

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- B. To promote the right to inform and to be informed accurately and independently, without impediments or discrimination;
 - C. To promote citizenship and democratic participation as well as to respect political, social and cultural pluralism;
 - D. To spread and promote the Portuguese culture and language, as well as values that express national identity;
 - E. To contribute towards the production and broadcasting of programmes, including information ones, aimed to the audience of the respective coverage area. ([1] art. 12)
-
- The radio broadcasting activity consisting in the organization of general or thematic information programme services on an international, national or regional level shall only be pursued, under this law, by legal bodies whose main purpose is to perform such activity.
The radio broadcasting activity consisting in the organization of general or thematic information programme services on a local level shall only be pursued, under this law, by legal bodies whose main purpose is to perform media activities. This shall not apply to associations or foundations pursuing humanitarian, educational, cultural, scientific or teaching goals, where the respective programme services significantly contribute to enhancing such activities. ([1] art. 15)
 - Licenses and authorizations for radio activity are issued for a period of 15 years and renewable for equal periods. ([1] art. 27)
 - Every programme service shall adopt an editorial statute that shall define clearly and in detail its orientation and objectives, including the commitment to respect the rights of listeners, professional ethics, as well as the deontological principles of journalists, where appropriate. ([1] art. 34)
 - Radio operators that provide general or thematic information programme services shall produce and broadcast at least three news services on a regular and daily basis, between 7 a.m. and 12 a.m. ([1] art. 35)
 - Programme services shall indicate their name and broadcasting frequency at least once every hour and wherever a segment of their own programmes restarts. ([1] art. 37)

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- Broadcasts shall be recorded and stored for at least 30 days, if a longer period is not determined by law or court decision. ([1] art. 39)
- The music programming of radio programme services must include Portuguese music with a minimum quota ranging from 25% to 40% (language, cultural heritage, portuguese culture) ([1] art. 41). Within this amount:
 - at least the 60% have to be composed or performed in Portuguese by citizens of the Member States of the European Union ([1] art. 43).
 - at least the 35% of music whose first phonographic edition or public communication has been made in the last 12 months (unless the program is about songs older than 1 year). ([1] art. 44)

[1] Law number 54 of the 24th of December 2010

<http://www.dre.pt/pdf1s/2010/12/24800/0590305918.pdf>

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